

THE EFFECTS OF MOISTURE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER PAPER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS/POLYAMIDE 6

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) has been widely used in different fields. From the viewpoint of low cost and the cohesiveness with carbon fiber, PA6 is inclined to be applicable. However, when evaluating the performance of products, environmental conditions are not neglectable. PA6 matrix composites are sensitive to environmental factors such as operation temperature and moisture from atmosphere. These factors will lead to the deterioration of mechanical properties which should be inhibited. In this study, the influence of moisture and temperature on the properties of carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics/polyamide 6 (CPT/PA6) materials was researched. Water absorption process of CPT/PA6 in fresh water was monitored. The kinetics of water absorption was studied by Fickian diffusion model. The temperature dependence and water content dependence of flexural properties were studied by three-point bending test. Temperatures were chosen from -25°C to 100°C and water contents were controlled from dry state to saturated state. The results show that the flexural strength and modulus have a sharp decrease as the water content increase in low water content rather than in high water content. The increase of operation temperature will have severe influence on the mechanical properties of CPT/PA6 materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

In modern society, energy shortage is one of the most severe problems faced by mankind. In terms of energy policy, human beings need to develop new energy and economize on expenditures of traditional energy to meet the increasing demands of energy consumption.

To date, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been widely applied in different fields including aerospace, civil engineering, automotive, sports goods, etc [1]. CFRP products have good mechanical properties and processability which makes its wide application probably [2,3]. When products can meet the same application requirements, CFRP has lower weight compared to ceramic and metal materials, so it can play a significant role in reducing fossil fuel consumption and is of great benefit to build an energy saving society. Among them, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have been researching due to their excellent properties.

Different kinds of CFRTP materials have been developed in recent years. Carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics (CPT) is one kind of advanced materials in the field of CFRTP. It is made by paper-making technique. Carbon fibers and polymer fibers are mixed in a tank filled with water. The mixed fibers are carefully stirred with a constant speed. After that, the water in the tank will be drawn, and the remaining fibers are left on the bottom of the tank. Then these fibers are dried and formed into CPT materials. CPT has high homogeneity and stable mechanical properties. Because of its good processability, it can be made into complicated shapes. Different matrices can be used such as polyamide (PA), polypropylene (PP), polycarbonate (PC), etc. [4-6]. Considering the cost control and the cohesiveness between carbon fibers and matrix, PA6 is expected to be applicable for mass-production application.

However, environment factors, including temperature, moisture and so on, will have negative effects on the service life of PA6 products [7,8]. The usability and security will decline, which will restrict the wide application of CFRTP and thereby indirectly increase the energy consumption.

In this research, the water diffusion process in CPT/PA6 specimens was studied. The effects of moisture and temperature on CPT/PA6 material were analysed. The flexural properties of this material will be estimated.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Material

The CPT/PA6 material used in this research was manufactured from CARMIX® made by Awa Paper Mfg. Co., Ltd. The volume fraction of carbon fiber is 24%.

2.2 Preparation of specimen

CPT/PA6 composite specimens were prepared by compression molding. Before molding, the CPT/PA6 materials were dried in a vacuum oven under 90°C for at least 24h. In the preheating stage, the temperature was set as 260°C, and the molding time was 15min. The pressure was kept as 1MPa. Then the pressure was removed for 3s to get rid of bubbles existing in the matrix. After that, the pressure was added to 5MPa and maintained until the end of molding process. After pressed for 10min at 5MPa, the molded plate was cooled to 50°C and taken out from the mold.

The molded plates were cut into specimens with a size of 120 mm×20 mm×3mm by a diamond disc cutter. The specimens were then dried in vacuum oven under 90°C for at least 72h to remove the remained water absorbed by PA6 during the cutting process.

2.3 Water absorption test

The effects of moisture were analyzed by water absorption test. The test was conducted in distilled water to analyze the water absorption property of CPT composite samples. Before immersed in distilled water, all the samples were dried in a vacuum oven at 90°C until their mass changes were less than 0.001%. Then these samples were immersed in water at 70°C which is higher than the glass transition temperature of PA6, in order to accelerate water absorption process.

The weight of specimens during the water absorption process was monitored. The weight gain ratio W (%) was calculated by the following equation:

$$W = \frac{m - m_0}{m_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where m_0 is the initial mass of specimen and m is the mass after certain time of water absorption.

According to Fick's diffusion law, the moisture distribution is solved subject to the initial and boundary conditions shown as following:

$$\begin{aligned} W &= W_0, 0 < z < h, t \leq 0 \\ W &= W_\infty, z = 0; z = h; t > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

W_0 is the initial water content, W_∞ is the maximum water content in specimen and h is the thickness of specimen.

So, the water diffusion can be described by using the following equation:

$$\frac{W - W_0}{W_\infty - W_0} = 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2n+1} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{h} \times \exp \left[-\frac{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 D t}{h^2} \right] \right) \quad (3)$$

D is the diffusion coefficient of water in specimen, which can be used to evaluate the diffusion ability of water.

Because the weight gain ratio changes with time, considering the initial time t_0 and any time t , the diffusion coefficient D can be written as

$$D = \frac{\pi h^2}{16} \left(\frac{k}{W_\infty} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where k is the initial slop of the plot of weight gain versus square root of time.

2.4 Three-point bending test

Three-point bending test was conducted in order to analyze the flexural properties of CPT/PA6 materials under different water contents and temperatures conditions. A universal testing machine (AUTOGRAPH AGXplus, Shimadzu Co.) was used. The load speed was 1 mm/min. The span of the supporters was determined by the thickness of specimens. The ratio of span to thickness was 16:1. The Three-point bending test was conducted at -25°C , 25°C , 75°C , and 100°C to detect the different performances of CPT/PA6 materials in a wide range of temperature. A thermostatic chamber was used to control the ambient temperature. The real-time temperatures of the surface of these specimens were monitored by a thermometer. Five specimens were tested under each condition.

The flexural strength and strain of these specimens can be calculated according to equation (5) and (6) as shown below.

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{600hS}{L^2} \quad (6)$$

where, σ_f is the flexural stress (MPa), F is the load (N), L is the test span (mm), h is the thickness of specimen (mm), b is the width of specimen (mm), S is the deflection (mm), and ε is strain (%). Stress-strain curves are drawn to analyze the flexural modulus of these specimens under different temperatures and water contents.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Water absorption test

The water absorption process can be analysed by Fick's law. The diffusion coefficient of water in specimen, D , can be used to evaluate water diffusing capacity [3]. The water absorption results are shown in Figure 1, and Figure 2 was drawn by weight gain versus square root of time following Fick's diffusion model. D can be calculated by the initial slope of water absorption curve in Figure 2. Relevant results are shown in Table 1. The average value of the maximum weight gain is 5.8% and D in fresh water at 70°C is $3.94 \times 10^{-8} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$.

Figure 1: The water absorption of CPT/PA6

Figure 2: Weight gain of CPT material with Fick's diffusion model

	$k (\times 10^{-3} \text{h}^{-1})$	$h (\times 10^{-3} \text{m})$	$W_{\infty} (\%)$	$D (\times 10^{-8} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h}^{-1})$
Sample 1	8.58	3.00	5.77	3.91
Sample 2	8.55	3.01	5.75	3.93
Sample 3	8.39	3.06	5.73	3.95
Sample 4	8.65	3.05	5.88	3.95
Sample 5	8.70	3.04	5.88	3.97

Table 1: Results of water absorption test.

Figure 3: The cross section of CPT material: a. dry specimen; b. saturated specimen

When the dry specimens were immersed into water, owing to the infinite gradient difference of water concentration between water medium and composites, the specimens absorbed water fast. As the water absorption proceeded, the difference of water concentration between the exterior and interior of specimens descended, which resulted in the decrease in the rate of water absorption.

Concerning the mechanism, the diffusion behavior is affected by the resin-rich area in composite and the interface between the fibers and resin. The SEM photo of cross section of dry specimen and saturated specimen are shown in Figure 3. Carbon fibers are evenly distributed in matrix in both two photos. In dry specimen, resin still remains on the surface of fibers which indicate the fiber-resin interface maintains a strong interaction. However, in saturated specimen, carbon fibers were pulled out from the matrix with little matrix bonded on the surface. This indicates that except for the hydrogen bond interaction with hydrophilic functional groups in the molecular chains, water also diffuses along the interface of fibers until saturated state.

3.2 Effects of water contents on flexural properties of CPT

Three-point bending test of CPT/PA6 material in different water contents was conducted. CPT specimens were controlled in dry state, half water absorbed state and saturated state. Ambient temperature was 25°C. The flexural strength and modulus of CPT material were obtained from the stress-strain curves, as shown in Figure 4 and Table 2.

State of specimens	Flexural strength (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)
Dry	407.3	8.955	18.04	0.2684
Half water absorbed	243.3	3.587	11.82	0.1227
Saturated	240.4	6.642	11.93	0.3262

Table 2: Flexural properties of CPT material in different water contents

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves of CPT material in different water contents

From Table 2, we can detect that the same weight gain ratio has differential influence on the mechanical properties of when the specimens in different water contents. From dry state to half-absorbed state, the strength and modulus of CPT have a sharp decrease. However, from half-absorbed state to saturated state, the strength and modulus did not change drastically. It can be considered that when the weight gain ratio reaches half of the maximum weight gain ratio, the subsequent water absorption behaviour will not have a significant influence on the properties of CPT. In other words, the initial stage of water absorption is fatal to maintain the mechanical properties of CPT material.

3.3 Effects of temperature on flexural properties of CPT

Three-point bending test of CPT/PA6 material in different temperatures was conducted. CPT specimens were kept in dry state. Ambient temperatures were controlled as mentioned above. The flexural strength and modulus of CPT material were obtained from the stress-strain curves, as shown in Figure 5 and Table 3.

As temperature rises, the flexural strength and modulus of CPT decrease owing to the thermal properties of PA6 resin. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of PA6 is around 55°C . When the ambient temperature is lower than T_g , the PA6 matrix is in the glassy state, which signifies slow molecular chain motion. Nevertheless, when the ambient temperature is higher than T_g , molecular chains move violently, and resins change to the rubber state, which led to the decline of flexural properties.

When the temperature rises by 50°C , the flexural strength at 25°C is only 21MPa lower than that at -25°C , and the flexural modulus almost unchanged. But the flexural strength at 75°C is 100MPa lower than that at 25°C , and the flexural modulus reduced 4GPa. This phenomenon consistent with the effects of glass transition temperature on the mechanical properties of materials.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curves of CPT material in different temperatures

Temperature	Flexural strength (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)
-25°C	428.7	9.420	18.64	0.1606
25°C	407.3	8.954	18.04	0.2685
75°C	307.7	4.629	14.65	0.3107
100°C	259.9	8.779	12.75	0.1281

Table 3: Flexural properties of CPT material in different temperatures

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the water absorption process of CPT/PA6 material was observed. The kinetics of water diffusion was analyzed, which is proved to conform to Fick's diffusion law.

Effects of different water contents and temperatures on the flexural properties of CPT/PA6 material were studied by using three-point bending test. When the weight gain ratio is the same, the flexural properties of specimens with low water content declined more than those with high water contents. Also, the flexural properties of CPT/PA6 material decrease as temperature increases, and the decrease ratio is higher at high temperature than at low temperature.

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